

“Viewers’ Perception and Preference towards Ott Platforms – A Study With Reference To Mangaluru City”

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Abstract

Over the past two decades, there has been a drastic change in the way people access and use video content. The age-old experience of watching TV is no longer limited to real-time or TV screen in the living room. Content is now used on laptops, tablets, etc- anytime and anywhere people want. Although not a household name in itself, OTT is the precise technology that has made the transition to broadcasting possible. The advent of online streaming platform such as Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, etc, means children and teenagers now have access to uncensored content, since there is no law or autonomous body to monitor and manage the digital contents provided on these OTT platforms and it is made available to the public at large without any filter or screening. As it is the case, OTT platforms should be responsible to create digital awareness i.e., viewers’ should be made aware of the impacts of their streaming and realise if there is really a need for watching those videos. Therefore, this study has been conducted to know the perception and preference of viewers’ towards OTT platforms and also to identify the factors influencing customers to use OTT.

Keywords: OTT platforms, traditional television experience

Introduction

Over the past two decades, there has been a drastic change in the way people access and use video content. The age-old experience of watching TV is no longer limited to real-time or TV screen in the living room. Traditional TV lacked the choices that consumers want, making them have to pay dearly for channels that they never watch. Content is now used on laptops, tablets, etc- anytime and anywhere people want. As the whole world has got access to broadband internet, many media platforms such as YouTube, Netflix, HBO, Disney+Hotstar and Amazon Prime emerged and gradually grew rapidly. These forums were a success by providing a media-hungry audience and keeping up with their increasingly busy lives. With the entry of OTT, consumers can access the content in a format that best fits their needs at any time, and from any place. In today’s world, we observe constant technological advancements in the mainstream media. As technology advances and consumer preferences shift, it is important for multiplexes and OTT platforms to differentiate themselves. With the emergence of OTT platforms, the viewing experience has been a drastic change. People are flocking to new and original content which the current multiplexes are finding hard to replicate. OTT has broken the order, and it is the multiplexes that are left to reel to counter this turbulent change.

Review of Literature

Rahul Ahuja (2020), in his research "A study on the effects of web series and streaming content on Indian youth," stated that the content being produced

and showcased on the online platforms is grabbing youth’s attention and moving them away from the traditional television soap operas. The study had been conducted to know the perception of youth regarding web series and online streaming content that is available on online platforms and also to examine the psychological effects and behavioral changes amongst the youth because of web shows. The study found that the content showcased on OTT platforms, filled with sexual, abusive, and violent content, together with alcohol and drugs, has caused psychological effects on Indian youth, who have suffered from insomnia, depression, and insecurities in their lives.

Bhavyarajsinh D (2021) in his research “A study on consumer behavior towards OTT platforms in India during covid era” stated that COVID-19 is an unpredictable global pandemic that changed the way audience consume media. This study specifies a trend surfaced in this period: the adoption of OTTs. Over the top media platform is a streaming media service offered directly to viewers via the internet. In India, there has been unprecedented growth in the number of consumers adapting to it. The study concluded that services like Hotstar and Jio Cinema has gained a stronger foot hold, global players like Netflix and Amazon Prime has grown tremendously in India.

Ponnumai K. (2022), in his research on "viewers satisfaction towards OTT platforms," opined that presently numerous OTT video platforms are available for consumers to encourage them. These OTT video platforms are developed to reach

customers easily through advanced provisions and technology. The main purpose of this study is to find out the perception and satisfaction of consumers or users of OTT video platforms. The study found that many consumers have subscribed to OTT video platform services to receive high-quality content in large quantities and without commercials. The study concluded that OTT platforms serve as a way for people to spend quality time with their friends and family. Even professionals who work from home have a flexible schedule and can spend time on OTT platforms.

Statement of the Problem

The advent of online streaming platform such as Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, etc, now have access to uncensored content, since there is no law or autonomous body to monitor and manage the digital contents provided on these OTT platforms and it is made available to the public at large without any filter or screening. As it is the case, OTT platforms should be responsible to create digital awareness i.e., consumers should be made aware of the impacts of their streaming and realize if there is really a need to watch those videos. And it's also viewer's responsibility to ensure that kids in our home do not access to such contents. This study deals with over-the-top platforms, and how these have brought a change in traditional television experience.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the perception and preference of viewers towards OTT platforms.
2. To know the factors influencing viewers to

Data Analysis And Interpretation

Table 4.1 Preference of Ott Platform For Watching Movies And Tv Shows

Ott Platforms	No. Of Responses	Percentage
Netflix	61	31.94
Amazon prime	45	23.56
Disney+Hotstar	46	24.08
Zee5	26	13.61
Other	13	6.81
TOTAL	191	100

Source: Survey data

M.R.R=1.91

N=100

Note:

1. **Total number of respondents is not equal to total number of responses, N=100, multiple response=191.**
2. **Multiple Response Rate is equal to the total number of responses divided by the Number of respondents.**

Analysis And Interpretation

There are multiple responses from the respondents about their preference for OTT platforms for watching movies and TV shows. From the above table 4.1, it is depicted that out of 100 respondents, 31.94% of the respondents prefer

use OTT platforms.

3. To know the satisfaction level of the viewers towards the OTT platforms.

Research Methodology

The study has been conducted to know the perception and preference of viewers towards OTT platforms. For the purpose of the study, both primary and secondary data have been collected. secondary data is collected from journals and the internet. Based on the requirements convenience samples have been selected and with the help of a structured questionnaire method and interview the information have been gathered from the viewers of OTT in Mangaluru City of Dakshina Kannada district who are from different areas. The data collected from various respondents have been analysed, has been organized in tabular form, and has been analysed with the help of different statistical tools such as average, and percentage to draw a meaningful conclusion. The sample size is 100. Samples were selected using convenience sampling method.

Limitations of The Study

The constraints to the study mainly were as follows:

1. An interpretation of this study is based on the assumption that respondents have given all correct answer.
2. Lack of willingness on part of the respondents has made the study difficult.
3. Time constraints has made the study difficult.
4. The findings of the study cannot be generalized.

Netflix, 24.08% of the respondents prefer Disney + Hotstar, 23.56% of the respondents prefer Amazon prime, 13.61% of the respondents prefer zee5, and only 6.81% of the respondents prefer other OTT platforms such as sony, voot, jio cinema etc. to watch movies and TV shows.

Based on the above analysis, it has been interpreted that the majority of the respondents, i.e., 31.94% prefer Netflix for watching movies and TV shows.

Table 4.2 Most Preferred Shows On Ott

SHOWS	NO. OF RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE
Movies	78	43.82
Series	64	35.96
Originals	16	8.99
Comedy exclusive	18	10.11
Other	2	1.12
TOTAL	178	100

Source: Survey data M.R.R=1.78 N=100

Note:

1. **Number of respondents is not equal to Number of responses, N=100, multiple response=178.**
2. **Multiple Response Rate is equal to the total number of responses divided by the Number of respondents.**

Analysis And Interpretation

There are multiple responses relating to the most preferred shows on OTT platforms. From the above table 4.2, it is clear that out of 100

respondents, 43.82% of the respondents watch movies on OTT platforms, 35.96% of the respondents watch series on OTT platforms, 10.11% of the respondents watch comedy exclusives on OTT platforms, 8.99% of the respondents watch originals and 1.12% of the respondents watch other contents like reality shows, clips etc.

Based on the above analysis, it has been interpreted that majority of the respondents, i.e., 43.82% prefer movies as the most preferred shows on OTT platform.

Table 4.3 Factors Influencing The Subscription Of Ottplatforms

Factors	No. Of Responses	Percentage
Convenience	50	32.05
Variety of content	70	44.87
Cost-friendly	23	14.74
OTT live streaming	12	7.70
Other	1	0.64
TOTAL	156	100

Source: Survey data

M.R.R=1.56

N=100

Note:

1. **Number of respondents is not equal to number of responses, N=100, multiple response=156**
2. **Multiple Response Rate is equal to the total number of responses divided by the Number of respondents.**

Analysis And Interpretation

There are multiple responses relating to the factors influencing the subscription to OTT platforms. From the above table 4.3, it is clear that out of 100 respondents, 44.87% of the respondents

are influenced by the variety of content that drives them towards OTT platforms, 32.05% of the respondents are influenced by the convenience factor, 14.74% of the respondents are influenced the by cost- friendly factor, 7.70% of the respondents are influenced by the OTT live streaming and the 0.64% of the respondents are influenced by other factors.

Based on the above analysis, it has been interpreted that the majority of the respondents, i.e., 44.87% are influenced by a variety of content.

Table 4.4 Ott Platforms Changed The Way Of Watching Television

Opinion	No. Of Responses	Percentage
Yes	90	90
No	10	10
TOTAL	100	100

Source: Survey dataN=100

Analysis and Interpretation

From the above table 4.4, it is clear that out of 100 respondents, 90% of the respondents stated that OTT platforms have changed the way of watching television and 10% of the respondents stated that OTT platforms have not changed the way

of watching television.

Based on the above analysis it has been interpreted that majority of the respondents, i.e., 90% stated that–“OTT platforms have changed the way of watching television”.

Table 4.4.1 Reasons For Change In The Way Of Watching Television

REASONS	NO. OF RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE
Ability to binge-watch the Entire season	48	27.58
More options to watch content On demand	44	25.29
Greater control over what to Watch and when	44	25.29
More options to customize Viewing experience	36	20.69
Other	2	1.15
TOTAL	174	100

Source: Survey data

M.R.R= 1.93

N=90

Note:

1. **Number of respondents is not equal to number of responses, N=90, multiple response=174.**
2. **Multiple Response Rate is equal to the total number of responses divided by the Number of respondents.**

Analysis And Interpretation

There are multiple responses relating to the reason for the change in the way of watching television. From the above table 4.4.1, Out of 90 respondents, 27.58% of the respondents feel the reason for change in the way of watching television due to OTT platform is ability to binge-watch the entire season, 25.29% of the respondents feel the reason for change in the way of watching television

due to OTT platform is more option to watch content on demand, and the otherb 25.29% of the respondents stated that greater control over what to watch and when is thebreason for change in the way of watching television, 20.69% of the respondents feel the reason for change in the way of watching television due to OTT platform is more options to customize the viewing experience and 1.15% of the respondents have other reasons.

Based on the above analysis, it has been interpreted that the majority of the respondents, i.e., 27.58% stated that ability to binge-watch the entire season is the reason for change in the way of watching television due to OTT platform.

Table 4.5 Level Of Satisfaction With Regard To The Usage Of Ott Platforms

Level Of Satisfaction	No. Of Responses	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	19	19
Satisfied	66	66
Neutral	14	14
Dissatisfied	1	1
Highly dissatisfied	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

Source:Survey data

N=100

Analysis And Interpretation

From the above table 4.5, it is clear that out of 100 respondents, 66% of the respondents are satisfied with the usage of OTT platforms, 19% of the respondents are highly satisfied, 14% of the respondents are neutral, 1% of the respondents are dissatisfied and none of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the usage of OTT platforms. Based on the above analysis, it has been interpreted that majority of the respondents, i.e., 66% are satisfied with the usage of OTT platforms.

Findings Of The Study

1. Majority of the respondents i.e., 31.94% of them

prefer Netflix for watching movies and TV shows.

2. This study found that majority of the respondents i.e., 43.82% of them prefer movies as the most preferred content in OTT platform.
3. Most of the respondents i.e., 44.87% of them are influenced by variety of content available on OTT platforms.
4. This study reveals that majority of the respondents i.e., 90% of them stated “OTT platforms have changed the way of watching television”.
5. This study reveals that majority of the

respondents i.e., 27.58 % of them feel that ability to binge-watch the entire season is the reason for change in the way of watching television due to OTT platform.

6. This study reveals that majority of the respondents i.e., 66% of them are satisfied with the usage of OTT platform.

Suggestions

1. The OTT platforms should recommend its users with new and featured content.
2. Better and effective subscription plans are to be introduced to cope up with the need for a majority of users who are occasionally consuming OTT platforms.
3. The relationship between the streaming platform and the consumers are to be strengthened through collection of critical user feedback which would help to maintain service excellence and retain the subscribers.
4. More attractive offers and promotions are to be made on the referral policy of the OTT platforms which would help in more new user acquisition.
5. The consumers should be made aware about the negative impact of sharing login details with others and also implement steps for resisting the same.
6. There should be more broadcasting of regional movies and programs which would give rise to an increased number of OTT consumers.

Conclusion

As India is the world's largest growing OTT industry, this momentum is utilized by the significant increase in the introduction of new OTT players in the market and rapid changes in providing of personalized content. Even the smaller OTT platforms are raising capital from international investors and making a significant impact on the market. It is quite evident that the arrival of COVID-19 pandemic has aided the OTT platforms with the increased consumption becoming the most preferred medium. The major benefits incurred from the OTT platforms are the flexibility of usage, availability of cross-cultural & worldwide entertainment and subscription to the user-friendly unlimited content. Also vital are factors like increasing penetration of Smart phones and availability of internet data at competitive prices in India. Movies and web series are the most preferred content on OTT platform Netflix, Amazon Prime Video and Disney+hotstar are the highest consumed OTT platforms as they satisfy their consumers with the best quality contents and user friendliness. There is also a huge rise in the arrival of regional OTT players in the market. Most of the current users of the OTT platforms are quite satisfied with their experience and majority of the consumers tend to increase their consumption of OTT in future. This trend can be

successfully explored by the different OTT platforms.

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